

THE IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING AND TEACHING VOCABULARY IN THE FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

The article deals with the importance of learning and teaching vocabulary in English. Vocabulary teaching methods and strategies are involved in research. The importance of translation, enumeration, active participation of students, creation of notebooks for vocabulary, connecting of words with semantic mapping are mentioned. Direct and indirect ways of learning vocabulary are also discussed.

Keywords: Vocabulary, learning styles, translation, vocabulary notebooks, direct and indirect vocabulary.

Introduction. Vocabulary always play an important part in learning a new language. Students benefit greatly from having a strong vocabulary as they work to master English's four main skills-listening, speaking, reading, and writing. One of the most talked-about aspects of teaching English as a foreign language is vocabulary instruction. The teacher needs to get ready and research the proper methods before implementing them with the learners. A skilled teacher should equip themselves with a variety of modern methods. To make students interested in and joyful about the teaching and learning process in the classroom, teachers must be able to master the content. A lot of emphasis is placed on teaching vocabulary learning procedures so that students can learn and recall new terms.

Users of effective vocabulary learning strategies are thought to be competent language learners. There is a clear connection between vocabulary and reading comprehension. Richards and Renandya made a similar point about the significance of vocabulary, contending that it plays a significant role in one's acquisition of a foreign language and linguistic ability and can influence how effectively speakers, listeners, readers, and writers perform [4]. Vocabulary should be viewed as a crucial component of language learning. Students who have mastered vocabulary are familiar with the meanings of words as well as their spoken and written forms, grammatical functions, word origins, collocations, register (spoken and written), associations (or connotations), and frequency (or frequency distribution) of the words. According to recent studies, it may be difficult to teach vocabulary since many teachers lack confidence in vocabulary teaching best practices and, at times, do not know how to start putting an instructional emphasis on word learning. Without words, it is nearly impossible to acquire a language. Words that students can recognize and comprehend when they are spoken in context are referred to as receptive vocabulary. It is language that students recognize when they read a text or come across it, but they don't utilize it when they talk or write.

Useful Vocabulary. Words that learners can grasp, pronounce correctly, and use effectively in speaking

and writing are known as productive vocabulary. Receptive vocabulary requirements as well as the capacity to speak or write at the proper time are included. Because students may create words to communicate their ideas to others, productive vocabulary can be handled as an active activity.

The Techniques in Teaching Vocabulary. There are typically a number of vocabulary teaching strategies. In order to keep students from forgetting, it must be learned, practiced, and corrected. The methods used by teachers are influenced by a number of factors, including the subject matter, time constraints, and the value to the students. This gives teachers justification for using particular methods of vocabulary presentation. Instead of using just one strategy to communicate a single intended vocabulary item, teachers frequently blend several different techniques

Utilizing Things. This method involves using real-world examples, visual aids, and demonstration. Given that human memory for objects and images is very dependable and that visual tactics can serve as cues for recalling words, they can aid students in learning vocabulary and helping them remember it better. When the vocabulary is made up of concrete nouns, objects can be utilized to demonstrate meanings [2]. They can facilitate young students' understanding and realization of the key concepts they have acquired in the classroom. By connecting knowledge to a new narrative, pictures help students acquire new words. Drawings or other images can be used to introduce a variety of language. They are incredibly effective at elucidating the meaning of obscure phrases. The list includes pictures of posters, flashcards, wall charts, magazine graphics, board drawings, stick figures, and photographs. Images for vocabulary education can be found in a variety of locations. As opposed to those made by the teacher or students, they are collections of colorful graphics designed for schools. Images that have been get from newspapers and magazines are also quite useful.

Contrast. Some words can be readily explained to students by comparison to their opposite, for example, Words "excellent" and "bad" were contrasted. Contrasting words whose reverse is gradable is practically impossible. Grey is the "in-between" word used when

the words "white" and "black" are juxtaposed. Additionally, the word "contrast" refers to demonstrate a distinction, as in pictures that contrast "before" and "after" pictures to demonstrate how much weight someone dropped. It is not unexpected that studying synonyms is a means to increase our vocabulary because numerous further research have demonstrated that vocabulary is best acquired when it is related to what has already been learned.

Enumeration. A collection of items is enumerated when every item in the collection is listed in full and in the correct sequence. It can be employed to convey message. In other words, this method is beneficial. By describing or enumerating several articles, we can use the word "clothing" to describe what we mean. When a teacher lists various articles of clothing, such as a dress, a skirt, or pants, the meaning of the word "clothes" becomes evident. The same applies to "furniture" or "vegetable," for instance.

Translation. Translation may be helpful for teachers in some situations, such as when dealing with incidental vocabulary evaluating students' comprehension, and pointing out similarities or differences between first and second language, when these are likely to cause errors. There are always certain words that need to be translated [5].

Students' Active Participation. By using this strategy, the teacher encourages the students to find the meaning of words from one another. Elicitation increases speaking opportunities for students and serves as a method of understanding student comprehension.

The word is the first brick laid for the existence of language. Each word to be added on it has an extremely important in preserving the language and transferring it to future generations. The factor that determines the strength and indestructibility of the resulting structure is the dictionaries prepared for this purpose. Although all researchers agree on the necessity of teaching vocabulary in a foreign language, there are different views on how this teaching should be done. The vocabulary in the texts of the books can be determined through practice; Through the teaching of words with visual support (pictures, gestures, activity and by means); Memorizing bilingual word lists; With the creation of word spaces and mind maps; Working with monolingual and bilingual dictionaries and other reference works; With the explanation and use of word structures (for example, word derivation, compound word derivation, collocations, phrasal verbs, idiom usages).

If the target word corresponds to a real object and can be brought into the classroom setting the real object is shown directly to the learners. Suitable for this technique the type of words is usually noun (Book, pen, table, apple, door, etc.). The target word is tried to be shown using gestures and mimics. This technique is mostly for the explanation of the meanings of concrete verbs and their adjectives associated with the emotional state of man. (Walking, sitting, laughing, crying, hitting; sad, happy, anxious, etc.).

If the teacher has a drawing ability, one of the types of pictures, figures and sketches that reflect the target word all are drawn on the board. It is possible to bring this technique to more educational environments.

(Forest, sea, river, sun; ride, die, collect, take out, flow, etc.). Pictures, posters and images taken from authentic materials such as newspapers and magazines or from the internet. The target word or words are tried to be taught through posters. For example, fruits related topics such as seasons, days, months, animals, clothes, tools and equipment. A poster with pictures of words is used in the teaching process [4]. Word cards, posters, interactive tools such as mobile applications, animations, and videos can also be used to teach vocabulary and understand the meaning of words can be used in explanation work. Expose students to the same word many times to support learning.

Creating vocabulary notebooks. Vocabulary notebooks encourage students to expand their prior knowledge and boost their English language proficiency. Teachers can motivate students to think about writing synonyms and antonyms beside each new word. To make vocabulary notebooks more fun a teacher draw pictures or create charts to show how they used a word in a few sentences. It gives them an opportunity to practice that word a few times and reinforce its definition. And speaking of opportunities, a perfect time for students to practice their language with vocabulary notebooks is during writing periods. These vocabulary word books remind students of their advancement. It'll help them realize just how much they've progressed throughout the year.

qConnect word meanings with semantic mapping. Semantic mapping is a type of graphic organizer that displays a relationship between specific words and phrases. For example, a student or teacher could write the keyword "farm" on the chalkboard. The students would take turns writing words such as cow, barn, horse, hay and farmer. Semantic maps help building students' vocabulary and reading comprehension. Teachers can add more challenging words each week. As students grow their vocabulary, they'll become confident in their reading and writing abilities. This technique can only be used if the relevant materials are available in the target language benefiting from visual elements in teaching words is also a concretization study. It will make significant contributions especially at fundamental levels [2]. With the help of words that target word learners have learned before, trying to explain at this point, it is necessary to determine which words the learners know at each level. Especially in the teaching of the words in the texts related to a certain field, directly teaching method needs to be preferred.

In order to learn the taught word permanently, repetition, reminder and multiple application is important. Vocabulary teaching activities require active participation of learners and is much more effective when it is designed in a way that allows.

Vocabulary learning styles differ depending on age of children and adults. Computer, mobile devices and applications and internet technology in vocabulary teaching should be used effectively as an auxiliary tool [3]. Giving and teaching words by associating them with visuals makes teaching more effective. It makes it fun and allows the words to be learned permanently. Activities that will enable learning should be prepared.

Words to be taught in different contexts should be presented and different teaching methods should be included in the process by not being content with a uniform teaching style. Attention should be drawn to the words that are thought to be unknown by the learners through emphasis and intonation.

Direct and indirect vocabulary learning. By learning lists of word forms and their definitions, engaging in vocabulary learning activities, or researching affixes and roots, one can acquire vocabulary directly by making a conscious effort to do so. Direct vocabulary learning can also be done by learning words out of context or in isolation. Indirect vocabulary learning occurs when new words are picked up by accident when reading or listening, typically as a result of the context's information [1]. The majority of vocabulary learning is by far indirect. It is impossible for a language course to cover all of the vocabulary necessary to read complicated material without difficulty due to the volume of vocabulary needed and the complexity of the learning process. A lot of reading and listening material can therefore promote indirect vocabulary learning. An essential vocabulary element of a language education is a well-structured, extended schedule of graded simple reading. Additionally, learners can receive practice using the methods for inferring word meanings from context.

A word's presentation and its meaning. When there is a relation between the display of a word form and its meaning, learners have the chance to guess the meaning, and it is assumed that this extra effort will lead to learning that is quicker and more easily maintained. The guessing, however, can only succeed if the

foreign word form provides a strong hint as to its meaning, either because the foreign and native words are cognates or because the word form and its translation have previously been observed together.

So vocabulary is the most important factor in teaching foreign language. It plays an important part in learning a new language. The teacher should be ready to research and teach the methods of teaching vocabulary. Some factors also affect vocabulary teaching process. The article emphasizes that learners should use the methods of learning and practicing so that they do not forget the words they have learned. Many vocabulary learning methods are discussed here. Among them is the translation method. It is noted that translation can be useful in some situations. Also, it is noted that notebooks with vocabulary are useful for students' motivation. Age and intelligence also affect the vocabulary learning process.

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